

1 NC-TODIM Based MAGDM under Neutrosophic 2 Cubic Set Environment

3 Surapati Pramanik ¹, Shyamal Dalapati ^{2,*}, Shariful Alam ² and Tapan Kumar Roy ²

4 ¹ Department of Mathematics, Nandalal Ghosh B.T. College, Panpur, P.O.-Narayanpur, District –North 24
5 Parganas, Pin code-743126, West Bengal, India; sura_pati@yahoo.co.in

6 ² Department of Mathematics, Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur, P.O.-Botanic
7 Garden, Howrah-711103, West Bengal, India; salam50in@yahoo.co.in (S.A.); roy_t_k@yahoo.co.in (T.K.R.)

8 * Correspondence: shyamal.rs2015@math.iiests.ac.in; Tel.: +91-9804234197

9 **Abstract:** Neutrosophic cubic set is the hybridization of the concept of neutrosophic set and interval
10 neutrosophic set. Neutrosophic cubic set has the capacity to express the hybrid information of both
11 the interval neutrosophic set and the single valued neutrosophic set simultaneously. As newly
12 defined, little research on the operations and applications of neutrosophic cubic sets appear in the
13 current literature. In the present paper we propose the score, accuracy functions for neutrosophic
14 cubic sets and prove their basic properties. We firstly develop TODIM method in neutrosophic cubic
15 set environment, which we call NC-TODIM. We establish a new NC-TODIM method in
16 neutrosophic cubic set environment for solving MAGDM in neutrosophic cubic set environment
17 problems. We illustrate the proposed NC-TODIM method for solving a MAGDM problem to show
18 applicability and effectiveness of the developed method. We also conduct sensitivity analysis to
19 show the impact of ranking order of the alternatives for different values of attenuation factor of
20 losses for multi-attribute group decision making problem.

21 **Keywords:** neutrosophic cubic set; single valued neutrosophic set; interval neutrosophic set; multi
22 attribute group decision making; TODIM method; NC-TODIM

23 1. Introduction

24 While modelling multi attribute decision making (MADM) and multi attribute group decision
25 making (MAGDM), it is often observed that the parameters of the problem are not precisely known.
26 The parameters often involve uncertainty. To deal uncertainty, Zadeh [1] left an important mark to
27 represent and compute with imperfect information by introducing fuzzy set. Fuzzy set fostered a
28 broad research community, and their impact has also been clearly felt at the application level in
29 MADM [2-4] and MAGDM [5-9].

30 Atanassov [10] incorporated non membership function as independent component and defined
31 intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) at first to express uncertainty in more meaningful way. IFSs have been
32 applied in many MADM problems [11-13]. Smarandache [14] proposed the notion of neutrosophic
33 set (NS) by introducing indeterminacy as independent component. Wang et al. [15] grounded the
34 concept of single valued neutrosophic set (SVNS), an instance of neutrosophic set to deal with
35 incomplete, inconsistent and indeterminate information in realistic way. Wang et al. [16] proposed
36 the interval neutrosophic sets (INS) as a subclass of neutrosophic sets in which the values of truth,
37 indeterminacy and falsity membership degrees are interval numbers. Applications of SVNSs and
38 INSs are found in [17-20] and [21-23] for MADM and MAGDM respectively.

39
40 Neutrosophic sets and INS are both capable of handling uncertainty and incomplete
41 information. By fusing neutrosophic set and INS, Ali et al. [24] proposed neutrosophic cubic set and
42 defined external and internal neutrosophic cubic sets and established some of their properties. Jun
43 et al. [25] also defined neutrosophic cubic set by combining neutrosophic set and INS. Neutrosophic
44 cubic set is more capable to express the hybrid information of both the INS and the SVNS
45 simultaneously. However, there are only few studies in the literature to deal with MADM and

46 MAGDM in neutrosophic cubic set environment. Banerjee et al. [26] developed grey relational
47 analysis [27-28] based new MADM method in neutrosophic cubic set environment.

48 Similarity measure is an important mathematical tool in decision-making problems.
49 Pramanik et al. [29] at first defined similarity measure for neutrosophic cubic sets and proved its
50 basic properties. In the same study, Pramanik et al. [29] developed a new MAGDM method in
51 neutrosophic cubic set environment. Lu and Ye [30] proposed cosine measures between
52 neutrosophic cubic sets and proved their basic properties. In the same study, Lu and Ye [30]
53 proposed a new cosine measures-based MADM method under a neutrosophic cubic environment.

54 Due to little research on operations and application of neutrosophic cubic sets, Pramanik et al.
55 [31] proposed several operational rules on neutrosophic cubic sets and defined Euclidean distance
56 and arithmetic average operator in neutrosophic cubic sets environment. Pramanik et al. [31] also
57 employed information entropy scheme to calculate unknown weights of the attributes and
58 developed a new extended TOPSIS method for MADM under neutrosophic cubic set environment.
59 Zhan et al. [32] developed a new algorithm for multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) in
60 neutrosophic cubic set environment based on weighted average operator and weighted geometric
61 operator. Ye [33] established the concept of a linguistic neutrosophic cubic number (LNCN). In the
62 same study, Ye [33] developed a new MADM method based on LNCN weighted arithmetic
63 averaging (LNCNWAA) operator and a LNCN weighted geometric averaging (LNCNWGA)
64 operator under a linguistic neutrosophic cubic environment.

65 In the literature there are only five methods [26-33] for MADM and MAGDM in neutrosophic
66 cubic set environment. However, we say that none of them is generally superior to all others. So,
67 new methods for MADM and MAGDM should be explored under neutrosophic cubic set
68 environment.

69 TODIM (an acronym in Portuguese for Interactive Multi-criteria Decision Making) is an
70 important MADM method, since it considers decision makers' bounded rationality. Firstly, Gomes
71 and Lima [34] introduced TODIM method based on prospect theory [35]. Krohling and Souza [36]
72 defined fuzzy TODIM method to solve MCDM problems. Several researchers applied fuzzy TODIM
73 method in various fuzzy MADM or MAGDM problems [37-39]. Fan et al [40] introduced extended
74 TODIM method to deal with the hybrid MADM problems. Krohling et al. [41] extended TODIM
75 method from fuzzy environment to intuitionistic fuzzy environment by extending TODIM method
76 to process the intuitionistic fuzzy information. Wang [42] introduced TODIM method to
77 neutrosophic environment. Zhang et al. [43] proposed TODIM method for MAGDM problems
78 under neutrosophic environment. Ji et al [44] proposed TODIM method under multi valued
79 neutrosophic environment and applied it to personal selection. In 2017, Xu et al. [45] develop
80 TODIM in single valued neutrosophic setting. In neutrosophic cubic set environment TODIM is yet
81 to appear. To fill the gap, we initiate the study of TODIM in neutrosophic cubic set environment
82 which we call as NC-TODIM.

83 In this paper we develop a TODIM method (for short, NC-TODIM method) for MAGDM in
84 neutrosophic cubic set environment. We solve an illustrative numerical example of MAGDM
85 problem in neutrosophic cubic set environment to show the applicability and effectiveness of the
86 proposed NC-TODIM method.

87 Remainder of the paper is divided into five sections that are organized as follows: Section
88 2 presents some basic definition of neutrosophic sets, interval-valued neutrosophic sets,
89 neutrosophic cubic sets. Section 3 is devoted to present the proposed NC-TODIM method. Section 4
90 presents an illustrative numerical example. Section 5 is devoted to analyse the ranking order with

91 different values of attenuation factor of losses. Finally, Section 6 presents conclusion and future
92 scope of research.

93 2. Preliminaries

94 In this section, we review some basic definitions which are important to develop the paper.

95 Definition 1. [14] Neutrosophic set (NS)

96 Let U be a space of points (objects) with a generic element in U denoted by u i.e. $u \in U$. A
97 neutrosophic set R in U is characterized by truth-membership function t_R , indeterminacy-
98 membership function i_R and falsity-membership function f_R , where t_R, i_R, f_R are the functions from
99 U to $]^{-0}, 1^+[$ i.e. $t_R, i_R, f_R : U \rightarrow]^{-0}, 1^+[$ that means $t_R(u), i_R(u), f_R(u)$ are the real standard
100 or non-standard subset of $]^{-0}, 1^+[$. Neutrosophic set can be expressed as $R = \{ \langle u; (t_R(u), i_R(u), f_R$
101 $(u)) \rangle : \forall u \in U \}$. Since $t_R(u), i_R(u), f_R(u)$ are the subset of $]^{-0}, 1^+[$, there the sum $(t_R(u) + i_R$
102 $(u) + f_R(u))$ lies between $^{-0}$ and 3^+ , where $^{-0} = 0 - \epsilon$ and $3^+ = 3 + \epsilon, \epsilon > 0$.

103 **Example 1.** Suppose that $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots\}$ be the universal set. Let R_1 be any neutrosophic set in U .
104 Then R_1 expressed as $R_1 = \{ \langle u_1; (.6, .3, .4) \rangle : u_1 \in U \}$.

105 Definition 2. [16] Interval neutrosophic set (INS)

106 Let G be a non-empty set. An interval neutrosophic set \tilde{G} in G is characterized by
107 truth-membership function $t_{\tilde{G}}$, the indeterminacy membership function $i_{\tilde{G}}$ and falsity
108 membership function $f_{\tilde{G}}$. For each $g \in G$, $t_{\tilde{G}}(g), i_{\tilde{G}}(g), f_{\tilde{G}}(g) \subseteq [0, 1]$ and \tilde{G} defined as
109 $\tilde{G} = \{ \langle g; [t_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), t_{\tilde{G}}^+(g)], [i_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), i_{\tilde{G}}^+(g)], [f_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), f_{\tilde{G}}^+(g)] \rangle : \forall g \in G \}$. Here, $t_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), t_{\tilde{G}}^+(g), i_{\tilde{G}}^-(g),$
110 $i_{\tilde{G}}^+(g), f_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), f_{\tilde{G}}^+(g) : G \rightarrow]^{-0}, 1^+[$ and
111 $^{-0} \leq \sup t_{\tilde{G}}^+(g) + \sup i_{\tilde{G}}^+(g) + \sup f_{\tilde{G}}^+(g) \leq 3^+$,

112 In real problems it is difficult to express the truth-memberships function,
113 indeterminacy-membership function and falsity-membership function in the form of $t_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), t_{\tilde{G}}^+(g),$
114 $i_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), i_{\tilde{G}}^+(g), f_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), f_{\tilde{G}}^+(g) : G \rightarrow]^{-0}, 1^+[$.
115 Here, $t_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), t_{\tilde{G}}^+(g), i_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), i_{\tilde{G}}^+(g), f_{\tilde{G}}^-(g), f_{\tilde{G}}^+(g) : G \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

116 Example 2.

117 Suppose that $G = \{g_1, g_2, g_3, \dots, g_n\}$ be a non-empty set. Let \tilde{G}_1 be any interval neutrosophic set. Then
118 \tilde{G}_1 expressed as $\tilde{G}_1 = \{ \langle g_1; [.39, .47], [.17, .43], [.18, .36] \rangle : g_1 \in G \}$.

119 Definition 3. [24] Neutrosophic cubic set (NCS)

120 A neutrosophic cubic set in a non-empty set G is defined as $\odot = \{ \langle g; \tilde{G}(g), R(g) \rangle : \forall g \in G \}$, where
121 \tilde{G} and R are the interval neutrosophic set and neutrosophic set in G respectively. Neutrosophic
122 cubic set can be presented as an order pair $\odot = \langle \tilde{G}, R \rangle$, then we call it as neutrosophic cubic number
123 (NC-number).

124 Example 3.

125 Suppose that $G = \{g_1, g_2, g_3, \dots, g_n\}$ be a non-empty set. Let \odot_1 be any NC-number. Then \odot_1 can be
126 express as $\odot_1 = \{ \langle g_1; [.39, .47], [.17, .43], [.18, .36], (.6, .3, .4) \rangle : g_1 \in G \}$

127 Some operations of NC-numbers:

128 i. Union of any two NC-numbers

129 Let $\odot_1 = \langle \tilde{G}_1, R_1 \rangle$ and $\odot_2 = \langle \tilde{G}_2, R_2 \rangle$ be any two NC-numbers in a non-empty set G . Then the
130 union of \odot_1 and \odot_2 denoted by $\odot_1 \cup \odot_2$ and defined as

131 $\odot_1 \cup \odot_2 = \langle \tilde{G}_1(g) \cup \tilde{G}_2(g), R_1(g) \cup R_2(g) \rangle : \forall g \in G$, where
132 $\tilde{G}_1(g) \cup \tilde{G}_2(g) = \{ \langle g, [\max \{ t_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), t_{\tilde{G}_2}^-(g) \}, \max \{ t_{\tilde{G}_1}^+(g), t_{\tilde{G}_2}^+(g) \}], [\max \{ i_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), i_{\tilde{G}_2}^-(g) \}, \max \{ i_{\tilde{G}_1}^+(g),$
133 $i_{\tilde{G}_2}^+(g) \}], [\min \{ f_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), f_{\tilde{G}_2}^-(g) \}, \min \{ f_{\tilde{G}_1}^+(g), f_{\tilde{G}_2}^+(g) \}] \rangle : g \in G$ and $R_1(g) \cup R_2(g) = \{ \langle g, \max \{ t_{R_1}(g),$
134 $t_{R_2}(g) \}, \max \{ i_{R_1}(g), i_{R_2}(g) \}, \min \{ f_{R_1}(g), f_{R_2}(g) \} \rangle : \forall g \in U \}$.

135

136 **Example 4.**137 Let \odot_1 and \odot_2 be two NC-numbers in G presented as follows:138 $\odot_1 = \langle [.39, .47], [.17, .43], [.18, .36], (.6, .3, .4) \rangle$ and $\odot_2 = \langle [.56, .70], [.27, .42], [.15, .26], (.7, .3, .6) \rangle$.139 Then $\odot_1 \cup \odot_2 = \langle [.56, .7], [.27, .43], [.15, .26], (.7, .3, .4) \rangle$.140 **ii. Intersection of any two NC-numbers**

141 Intersection of two NC-numbers denoted and defined as follows:

142 $\odot_1 \cap \odot_2 = \langle \tilde{G}_1(g) \cap \tilde{G}_2(g), R_1(g) \cap R_2(g) \forall g \in G \rangle$, where $\tilde{G}_1(g) \cap \tilde{G}_2(g) = \{ \langle g, [\min \{ t_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), t_{\tilde{G}_2}^-$ 143 $(g), \min \{ t_{\tilde{G}_1}^+(g), t_{\tilde{G}_2}^+(g) \}], [\min \{ i_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), i_{\tilde{G}_2}^-(g) \}, \min \{ i_{\tilde{G}_1}^+(g), i_{\tilde{G}_2}^+(g) \}], [\max \{ f_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), f_{\tilde{G}_2}^-$ 144 $\{ f_{\tilde{G}_1}^+(g), f_{\tilde{G}_2}^+(g) \}] \rangle: g \in G$ and $R_1(g) \cap R_2(g) = \{ \langle g, \min \{ t_{R_1}(g), t_{R_2}(g) \}, \min \{ i_{R_1}(g), i_{R_2}(g) \},$ 145 $\max \{ f_{R_1}(g), f_{R_2}(g) \} \rangle: \forall g \in U$.146 **Example 5.**147 Let \odot_1 and \odot_2 be any two NC-numbers in G presented as follows:148 $\odot_1 = \langle [.45, .57], [.27, .33], [.18, .46], (.7, .3, .5) \rangle$ and $\odot_2 = \langle [.67, .75], [.22, .44], [.17, .21], (.8, .4, .4) \rangle$.149 Then $\odot_1 \cap \odot_2 = \langle [.45, .57], [.22, .33], [.18, .46], (.7, .3, .4) \rangle$.150 **iii. Compliment of a NC-number**151 Let $\odot_1 = \langle \tilde{G}_1, R_1 \rangle$ be any neutrosophic cubic set in G . Then compliment of $\odot_1 = \langle \tilde{G}_1, R_1 \rangle$ 152 denoted by $\odot_1^c = \langle g, \tilde{G}_1^c(g), R_1^c(g) \rangle: \forall g \in G$.153 Here, $\tilde{G}_1^c = \{ \langle g, [t_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^-(g), t_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^+(g)], [i_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^-(g), i_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^+(g)], [f_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^-(g), f_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^+(g)] \rangle: \forall g \in G \}$, where, $t_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^-(g) =$ 154 $f_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), t_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^+(g) = f_{\tilde{G}_1}^+(g), i_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^-(g) = \{1\} - i_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), i_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^+(g) = \{1\} - i_{\tilde{G}_1}^+(g), f_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^-(g) = t_{\tilde{G}_1}^-(g), f_{\tilde{G}_1^c}^+(g) = f_{\tilde{G}_1}^+$ 155 (g) and $t_{R_1^c}(g) = f_{R_1}(g), i_{R_1^c}(g) = \{1^+\} - i_{R_1}(g), f_{R_1^c}(g) = t_{R_1}(g)$.156 **Example 6.**157 Assume that \odot_1 be any NC-number in G in the form:158 $\odot_1 = \langle [.45, .57], [.27, .33], [.18, .46], (.7, .3, .5) \rangle$. Then compliment of \odot_1 is obtained as $\odot_1^c = \langle [.18,$ 159 $.46], [.73, .67], [.45, .57], (.5, .7, .7) \rangle$.160 **Definition 4.** Score function161 Let \odot_1 be a NC-number in a non-empty set G . Then, a score function of \odot_1 ,162 $Sc(\odot_1)$ is defined as:

163
164
$$Sc(\odot_1) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{2+a_1+a_2-2b_1-2b_2-c_1-c_2}{4} \right) + \left(\frac{1+a-2b-c}{2} \right) \right] \quad (2.1)$$

165 where, $\odot_1 = \langle [a_1, a_2], [b_1, b_2], [c_1, c_2], (a, b, c) \rangle$ and $Sc(\odot_1) \in [-1, 1]$.166 **Proposition 1.** Score function of two NC-numbers lies between -1 to 1.167 **Proof.**168 Using the definition of interval neutrosophic set and neutrosophic set, we have all $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_1, c_2,$ 169 $a, b,$ and $c \in [0, 1]$.170 Since, $0 \leq a_1 \leq 1, 0 \leq a_2 \leq 1$

171
$$\Rightarrow 0 \leq a_1 + a_2 \leq 2,$$

172
$$\Rightarrow 2 \leq 2 + a_1 + a_2 \leq 4 \quad (2.2)$$

173
$$0 \leq b_1 \leq 1 \Rightarrow 0 \leq 2b_1 \leq 2, \text{ and } 0 \leq b_2 \leq 1 \Rightarrow 0 \leq 2b_2 \leq 2$$

174
$$\Rightarrow -2 \leq -2b_1 \leq 0$$

175
$$\Rightarrow -2 \leq -2b_2 \leq 0$$

$$176 \quad \Rightarrow -4 \leq -2b_1 - 2b_2 \leq 0 \quad (2.3)$$

$$177 \quad 0 \leq c_1 \leq 1 \Rightarrow -1 \leq -c_1 \leq 0$$

$$178 \quad 0 \leq c_2 \leq 1 \Rightarrow -1 \leq -c_2 \leq 0$$

$$179 \quad \Rightarrow -2 \leq -c_1 - c_2 \leq 0 \quad (2.4)$$

180 Adding (2.2), (2.3) and (2.4), we obtain

$$181 \quad \Rightarrow -4 \leq 2 + a_1 + a_2 - 2b_1 - 2b_2 - c_1 - c_2 \leq 4,$$

$$182 \quad \Rightarrow -1 \leq \frac{2 + a_1 + a_2 - 2b_1 - 2b_2 - c_1 - c_2}{4} \leq 1 \quad (2.5)$$

183 Again,

$$184 \quad 0 \leq a \leq 1 \Rightarrow 1 \leq 1 + a \leq 2, \quad (2.6)$$

$$185 \quad 0 \leq b \leq 1 \Rightarrow 0 \leq 2b \leq 2,$$

$$186 \quad 0 \leq c \leq 1,$$

$$187 \quad \Rightarrow 0 \leq 2b + c \leq 3,$$

$$188 \quad \Rightarrow -3 \leq -2b - c \leq 0 \quad (2.7)$$

189 Adding (2.6) and (2.7), we obtain

$$190 \quad -2 \leq 1 + a - 2b - c \leq 2,$$

$$191 \quad \Rightarrow -1 \leq \frac{1 + a - 2b - c}{2} \leq 1 \quad (2.8)$$

192 Adding (2.5) and (2.8) and dividing by 2, we obtain

$$193 \quad -1 \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{2 + a_1 + a_2 - 2b_1 - 2b_2 - c_1 - c_2}{4} \right) + \left(\frac{1 + a - 2b - c}{2} \right) \right] \leq 1$$

$$194 \quad \text{Sc}(\odot_1) \in [-1, 1],$$

195 Hence complete the proof.

196 **Example 7.**

197 Let \odot_1 and \odot_2 be two NC-numbers in G presented as follows:

$$198 \quad \odot_1 = \langle [.39, .47], [.17, .43], [.18, .36], (.6, .3, .4) \rangle \text{ and } \odot_2 = \langle [.56, .70], [.27, .42], [.15, .26], (.7, .3, .6) \rangle.$$

199 Then, by applying Definition 4, we obtain $\text{Sc}(\odot_1) = -.01$ and $\text{Sc}(\odot_2) = .07$. In this case, we can say

200 that $\odot_2 > \odot_1$.

201 **Definition 5.** Accuracy function

202 Let \odot_1 be a NC-number in a non-empty set G , an accuracy function of \odot_1 is defined as:

$$\text{Ac}(\odot_1) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{2} (a_1 + a_2 - b_2(1-a_2) - b_1(1-a_1) - c_2(1-b_1) - c_1(1-b_2)) + a - b(1-a) - c(1-b) \right] \quad (2.9)$$

Here, $\text{Ac}(\odot_1) \in [-1, 1]$.

When the value of $\text{Ac}(\odot_1)$ increases, we say that the degree of accuracy of the NC-number \odot_1 increases.

Proposition 2. Accuracy function of two NC-numbers lies between -1 to 1.

Proof.

The values of accuracy function depend upon

$\left\{ \frac{1}{2} (a_1 + a_2 - b_2(1-a_2) - b_1(1-a_1) - c_2(1-b_1) - c_1(1-b_2)) \right\}$ and $\{a - b(1-a) - c(1-b)\}$ The values of

$\left\{ \frac{1}{2} (a_1 + a_2 - b_2(1-a_2) - b_1(1-a_1) - c_2(1-b_1) - c_1(1-b_2)) \right\}$ and $\{a - b(1-a) - c(1-b)\}$ lies between -1 to 1 from [18].

Thus, $-1 \leq \text{Ac}(\odot_1) \leq 1$.

Hence complete the proof.

Example 8.

Let \odot_1 and \odot_2 be two NC-numbers in G

presented as follows: $\odot_1 = \langle [41, .52], [10, .18], [06, .17], (.48, .11, .11) \rangle$ and

$\odot_2 = \langle [40, .51], [10, .20], [10, .19], (.50, .11, .11) \rangle$. Then, by applying Definition 5, we obtain $\text{Ac}(\odot_1) = .14$

and $\text{Ac}(\odot_2) = .30$. In this case, we can say that alternative \odot_2 is better than \odot_1 .

With respect to the score function Sc and the accuracy function Ac , a method for comparing NC-numbers can be defined as follows:

225 Comparison procedure of two NC-numbers

Let \odot_1 and \odot_2 be any two NC-numbers. Then we define comparison method as follows:

i. If $Sc(\odot_1) > Sc(\odot_2)$, then $\odot_1 > \odot_2$. (2.10)

ii. If $Sc(\odot_1) = Sc(\odot_2)$ and $Ac(\odot_1) > Ac(\odot_2)$, then $\odot_1 > \odot_2$. (2.11)

iii. If $Sc(\odot_1) = Sc(\odot_2)$ and $Ac(\odot_1) = Ac(\odot_2)$, then $\odot_1 = \odot_2$. (2.12)

230 Example 9.

Let \odot_1 and \odot_2 be two NC-numbers in G presented as follows:

$\odot_1 = \langle [23, .29], [37, .46], [34, .42], (.26, .26, .26) \rangle$ and

$\odot_2 = \langle [25, .31], [35, .44], [35, .44], (.28, .28, .28) \rangle$. Then, applying Definition 4, we obtain $Sc(\odot_1) = .13$ and

$Sc(\odot_2) = .13$. Applying Definition 5, we obtain $Ac(\odot_1) = -.20$ and $Ac(\odot_2) = -.18$. In this case, we say

that alternative $\odot_2 > \odot_1$. (Score values and Accuracy values taking correct up to two decimal

places)

237 Definition 6.

Let \odot_1 and \odot_2 be any two NC-numbers, then distance between them is defined by

$$\partial(\odot_1, \odot_2) = \frac{1}{9} [|a_1 - d_1| + |a_2 - d_2| + |b_1 - e_1| + |b_2 - e_2| + |c_1 - f_1| + |c_2 - f_2| + |a - d| + |b - e| + |c - f|] \quad (2.13)$$

where, $\odot_1 = \langle [a_1, a_2], [b_1, b_2], [c_1, c_2], (a, b, c) \rangle$ and $\odot_2 = \langle [d_1, d_2], [e_1, e_2], [f_1, f_2], (d, e, f) \rangle$.

241 Example 10.

Let \odot_1 and \odot_2 be two NC-numbers in G presented as follows:

243 $\odot_1 = \langle [.66, .75], [.25, .32], [.17, .34], (.53, .17, .22) \rangle$ and $\odot_2 = \langle [.35, .55], [.12, .25], [.12, .20], (.60, .23,$
 244 $.43) \rangle$. Then, applying Definition 6, we obtain $\partial (\odot_1, \odot_2) = .12$.

245 **Definition 7.**

246 Let $\odot_{ij} = \{ \langle [t_{ij}^-, t_{ij}^+], [i_{ij}^-, i_{ij}^+], [f_{ij}^-, f_{ij}^+], (t, i, f) \rangle \}$ be any neutrosophic cubic value. \odot_{ij} used to
 247 evaluate i -th alternative with respect to j -th criterion. The normalized form of \odot_{ij} is defined
 248 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 249 \quad \odot_{ij}^{\otimes} = & \left\langle \left[\frac{t_{ij}^-}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (t_{ij}^-)^2 + (t_{ij}^+)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \frac{t_{ij}^+}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (t_{ij}^-)^2 + (t_{ij}^+)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right], \left[\frac{i_{ij}^-}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (i_{ij}^-)^2 + (i_{ij}^+)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \frac{i_{ij}^+}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (i_{ij}^-)^2 + (i_{ij}^+)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right], \right. \\
 250 \quad & \left. \left[\frac{f_{ij}^-}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (f_{ij}^-)^2 + (f_{ij}^+)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \frac{f_{ij}^+}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (f_{ij}^-)^2 + (f_{ij}^+)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right] \right. \\
 251 \quad & \left. \left[\frac{t_{ij}}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (t_{ij})^2 + (i_{ij})^2 + (f_{ij})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \frac{i_{ij}}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (t_{ij})^2 + (i_{ij})^2 + (f_{ij})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \frac{f_{ij}}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^m (t_{ij})^2 + (i_{ij})^2 + (f_{ij})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right] \right\rangle. \quad (2.14)
 \end{aligned}$$

252 2.1. A conceptual model of evolution of neutrosophic cubic set is shown in Figure 1.

270 Figure.1. Evolution of neutrosophic cubic set

271

272 3. NC-TODIM method for solving MAGDM problem under neutrosophic cubic set 273 environment

274 Classical TODIM is not enough to deal neutrosophic MAGDM problems due to
 275 presence of indeterminacy and complexity of decision environment. However, NC-numbers
 276 can express the indeterminate information. In this study we extend the TODIM method to
 277 NC-TODIM to solve the MAGDM problems under neutrosophic cubic set environment.

278 3.1. Description about MAGDM problems

279 Assume that $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m\}$ ($m \geq 2$), $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$ ($n \geq 2$) be the discrete set of
 280 alternatives and attributes respectively. $W = \{W_1, W_2, \dots, W_n\}$ is the weight vector of attribute
 281 C_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), where $W_j > 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n W_j = 1$. Let $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_r\}$ be the set of decision
 282 makers and $\gamma = \{\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_r\}$ be the weight vector of decision makers, where $\gamma_k > 0$ and $\sum_{k=1}^r \gamma_k = 1$

283 3.2. NC-TODIM method

284 Now, we describe the procedure of NC-TODIM method to solve the MAGDM
 285 problems with NC-numbers. The method consists of following steps:

286 **Step1. Formulate the decision matrix**

287 Assume that $M^k = (\odot_{ij}^k)_{m \times n}$ be the decision matrix, where $\odot_{ij}^k = \langle \tilde{G}_{ij}^k, R_{ij}^k \rangle$ is the rating
 288 value provided by the decision maker E_k for alternative A_i with respect to attribute C_j . The
 289 matrix form of M^k is presented below

$$290 \quad M^k = \begin{pmatrix} & C_1 & C_2 & \dots & C_n \\ A_1 & \odot_{11}^k & \odot_{12}^k & \dots & \odot_{1n}^k \\ A_2 & \odot_{21}^k & \odot_{22}^k & & \odot_{2n}^k \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \\ A_m & \odot_{m1}^k & \odot_{m2}^k & \dots & \odot_{mn}^k \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

291 **Step 2. Normalize the decision matrix**

292 MAGDM problem generally consists of cost criteria and benefit criteria. So, the
 293 decision matrix needs to be normalized. For cost criterion C_j we use the Equation (7) to
 294 normalize the decision matrix (Equation (3.1)) provided by the decision makers. For benefit
 295 criterion C_j we don't need to normalize the decision matrix. When C_j is a cost criterion, the
 296 normalized form of decision matrix (see Equation (3.1)) is presented below.

$$297 \quad M^{\otimes k} = \begin{pmatrix} & C_1 & C_2 & \dots & C_n \\ A_1 & \odot_{11}^{\otimes k} & \odot_{12}^{\otimes k} & \dots & \odot_{1n}^{\otimes k} \\ A_2 & \odot_{21}^{\otimes k} & \odot_{22}^{\otimes k} & & \odot_{2n}^{\otimes k} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \\ A_m & \odot_{m1}^{\otimes k} & \odot_{m2}^{\otimes k} & \dots & \odot_{mn}^{\otimes k} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.2)$$

298 Here $\odot_{ij}^{\otimes k}$ is the normalized form of NC-number.

299 **Step 3. Determine the relative weight of each criterion**

300 Relative weight W_{ch} of each criterion is obtained by the following equation.

$$301 \quad W_{ch} = \frac{W_c}{W_h} \quad (3.3)$$

302 where, $W_h = \max \{W_1, W_2, \dots, W_n\}$.

303 **Step 4. Calculate score values**

304 Using Equation (2.1), calculate score value $Sc(\odot_{ij}^{\otimes k})$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) of $\odot_{ij}^{\otimes k}$ if C_j is a
 305 cost criterion. Using Equation (2.1), calculate score value $Sc(\odot_{ij}^k)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) of \odot_{ij}^k
 306 if C_j is a benefit criterion.

307 Step 5: Calculate accuracy values

308 Using Equation (2.9), calculate accuracy value $Ac(\odot_{ij}^{\otimes k})$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) of $\odot_{ij}^{\otimes k}$ if C_j is a
 309 cost criterion. Using Equation (2.9), calculate accuracy value $Ac(\odot_{ij}^k)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) of
 310 \odot_{ij}^k if C_j is a benefit criterion.

311 Step 6. Formulate the dominance matrix

312 Calculate the dominance of each alternative A_i over each alternative A_j with respect to the criteria C
 313 (C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n) , of the k -th decision maker E_k by the following Equation (3.4) and Equation (3.5).
 314 (For cost criteria)

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 \Psi_c^k(A_i, A_j) &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{W_{Ch}}{\sum_{c=1}^n W_{ch}} \right) \partial(\odot_{ic}^{\otimes k}, \odot_{jc}^{\otimes k}), \text{ if } \odot_{ic}^{\otimes k} > \odot_{jc}^{\otimes k}} \\
 &= 0, \text{ if } \odot_{ic}^{\otimes k} = \odot_{jc}^{\otimes k} \\
 &= -\frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sum_{c=1}^n W_{ch}}{W_{Ch}} \right) \partial(\odot_{ic}^{\otimes k}, \odot_{jc}^{\otimes k}), \text{ if } \odot_{ic}^{\otimes k} < \odot_{jc}^{\otimes k}}
 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.4)$$

316 (For benefit criteria)

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 \Psi_c^k(A_i, A_j) &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{W_{Ch}}{\sum_{c=1}^n W_{ch}} \right) \partial(\odot_{ic}^k, \odot_{jc}^k), \text{ if } \odot_{ic}^k > \odot_{jc}^k} \\
 &= 0, \text{ if } \odot_{ic}^k = \odot_{jc}^k \\
 &= -\frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sum_{c=1}^n W_{ch}}{W_{Ch}} \right) \partial(\odot_{ic}^k, \odot_{jc}^k), \text{ if } \odot_{ic}^k < \odot_{jc}^k}
 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.5)$$

318 Where, parameter ' α ' represents the attenuation factor of losses and α must be positive.

319 Step 7. Formulate the individual total dominance matrix

320 Using Equation (3.6), calculate the individual total dominance matrix of each alternative A_i over each
 321 alternative A_j .

$$\lambda^k(A_i, A_j) = \sum_{c=1}^n \Psi_c^k(A_i, A_j) \quad (3.6)$$

323 Step 8. Aggregate the dominance matrix

324 Using Equation (3.7), calculate the collective overall dominance of alternative A_i over each
 325 alternative A_j .

$$326 \quad \lambda(A_i, A_j) = \sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_k \lambda^k(A_i, A_j) \quad (3.7)$$

327 Step 9. Calculate global values

328 Using the Equation (3.8), we calculate global value of each alternative

$$329 \quad \Omega_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda(A_i, A_j) - \min_{l \leq i \leq m} (\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda(A_l, A_j))}{\max_{l \leq i \leq m} (\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda(A_i, A_j)) - \min_{l \leq i \leq m} (\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda(A_l, A_j))} \quad (3.8)$$

330 Step 10. Rank the priority

331 Sorting the values of Ω_i provides the rank of each alternative. A set of alternatives can be preference
 332 ranked according to the descending order of Ω_i . Highest global value corresponds to the best
 333 alternative.

334 3.3. A conceptual model of the proposed approach is shown in Figure 2.

355 Figure 2: A flow chart of the proposed method.

356
 357
 358
 359

360 4. Illustrative example

361 In this section, a MAGDM problem is adapted from the study [18] under neutrosophic cubic set
 362 environment. An investment company wants to select a best alternative among the set of feasible
 363 alternatives. The feasible alternatives are

- 364 1. Car company (A_1)
- 365 2. Food company (A_2)
- 366 3. Computer company (A_3)
- 367 4. Arms company (A_4)

368 The best alternative is selected based on the following criteria:

- 369 1. Risk analysis (C_1)
- 370 2. Growth analysis (C_2)
- 371 3. Environmental impact analysis (C_3)

372 An investment company forms a panel of three decision makers $\{E_1, E_2, E_3\}$ who evaluate four
 373 alternatives in decision making process. The weight vector of attributes and decision makers are
 374 considered as $W = (.4, .35, .25)^T$ $\gamma = (.32, .33, .35)^T$ respectively.

375 The proposed method is presented using the following steps:

376 Step 1. Formulate the decision matrix

377 Formulate the decision matrices $M^k (k=1,2,3)$ using the rating values of alternatives with respect
 378 to three criteria provided by the three decision makers in terms of neutrosophic cubic numbers.

379 Assume that the NC-numbers $\odot_{ij}^k = \langle \tilde{G}_{ij}^k, R_{ij}^k \rangle$ presents rating value provided by the decision
 380 maker E_k for alternative A_i with respect to attribute C_j . Using these rating values $\odot_{ij}^k (k=1, 2, 3; i=1,$

381 $2, 3, 4; j=1, 2, 3)$, three decision matrices $M^k = (\odot_{ij}^k)_{4 \times 3} (k=1, 2, 3)$ are constructed (see Equations
 382 (4.1), (4.2) and (4.3)).

383 Decision matrix for E_1

$$384 M^1 = \begin{pmatrix} & C_1 & & C_2 & & C_3 \\ A_1 & \langle [41,52][.10,18][.06,17](.48,11,.11) \rangle & & \langle [40,51][.10,20][.10,19](.50,11,.11) \rangle & & \langle [22,27][.41,52][.41,52](.31,31,31) \rangle \\ A_2 & \langle [35,46][.18,27][.17,34](.43,16,21) \rangle & & \langle [22,28][.40,50][.39,48](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [38,49][.10,21][.10,21](.57,12,12) \rangle \\ A_3 & \langle [23,29][.36,45][.34,42](.26,26,26) \rangle & & \langle [34,45][.20,30][.19,39](.44,16,22) \rangle & & \langle [22,27][.41,52][.41,52](.31,31,31) \rangle \\ A_4 & \langle [17,23][.45,55][.42,59](.21,32,37) \rangle & & \langle [22,28][.40,50][.39,48](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [38,49][.10,21][.10,21](.57,12,12) \rangle \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

385 Decision matrix for E_2

$$386 M^2 = \begin{pmatrix} & C_1 & & C_2 & & C_3 \\ A_1 & \langle [17,23][.46,55][.42,59](.21,32,37) \rangle & & \langle [25,31][.35,44][.35,44](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [34,43][.13,27][.13,27](.49,11,11) \rangle \\ A_2 & \langle [23,29][.37,46][.34,42](.26,26,26) \rangle & & \langle [25,31][.35,44][.35,44](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [34,43][.13,27][.13,27](.49,11,11) \rangle \\ A_3 & \langle [41,52][.10,18][.10,17](.48,11,.11) \rangle & & \langle [44,57][.10,17][.10,17](.51,11,.11) \rangle & & \langle [19,24][.53,67][.53,67](.27,27,27) \rangle \\ A_4 & \langle [35,46][.20,28][.17,34](.42,16,21) \rangle & & \langle [25,31][.35,44][.35,44](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [34,43][.13,27][.13,27](.49,11,11) \rangle \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.2)$$

387 Decision matrix for E_3

$$388 M^3 = \begin{pmatrix} & C_1 & & C_2 & & C_3 \\ A_1 & \langle [22,27][.42,52][.42,52](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [22,28][.40,50][.39,48](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [41,52][.10,18][.10,17](.48,11,.11) \rangle \\ A_2 & \langle [22,27][.42,52][.42,52](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [40,51][.10,20][.10,19](.50,11,.11) \rangle & & \langle [23,29][.36,45][.34,42](.26,26,26) \rangle \\ A_3 & \langle [38,49][.10,21][.10,21](.50,11,.11) \rangle & & \langle [34,45][.20,30][.19,39](.44,16,22) \rangle & & \langle [38,49][.10,21][.10,21](.50,11,.11) \rangle \\ A_4 & \langle [38,49][.10,21][.10,21](.50,11,.11) \rangle & & \langle [22,28][.40,50][.39,48](.28,28,28) \rangle & & \langle [17,23][.45,54][.42,59](.21,32,37) \rangle \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.3)$$

389

390 **Step 2. Normalize the decision matrix**

391 Since all the criteria are benefit type, we do not need to normalize the decision matrix.

392 **Step 3. Determine the relative weight of each criterion**393 Using Equation (3.3), we obtain the relative weight of criteria W_{ch} as follows:

394
$$W_{ch} = (1, .875, .625)^T.$$

395 **Step 4. Calculate score values**396 The score values of each alternative relative to each criterion obtained by Equation (2.1) are presented in the
397 Tables 1, 2 and 3.

398

399 Table 1. Score values for M^1 .

	C_1	C_2	C_3
A ₁	.56	.54	.06
A ₂	.40	.09	.54
A ₃	.50	.38	.06
A ₄	-.03	.09	.54

400 Table 2. Score values for M^2

	C_1	C_2	C_3
A ₁	-.03	.13	.49
A ₂	.13	.13	.49
A ₃	.56	.60	-.04
A ₄	.39	.13	.49

401 Table 3. Score values for M^3

	C_1	C_2	C_3
A ₁	.07	.09	.56
A ₂	.07	.52	.13
A ₃	.51	.37	.39
A ₄	.51	.09	-.03

402 **Step 5. Calculate accuracy values**403 The accuracy values of each alternative relative to each criterion obtained by Equation (2.9). are presented in
404 Tables 4, 5 and 6.

405

406

407

Table 4. Accuracy values for M¹.

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃
A ₁	.14	.30	-.24
A ₂	.12	-.23	.32
A ₃	-.20	.09	-.24
A ₄	-.38	-.23	.32

408

Table 5. Accuracy values for M².

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃
A ₁	-.38	-.18	.21
A ₂	-.20	-.18	.21
A ₃	.14	.36	-.21
A ₄	.12	-.18	.21

409

Table 6. Accuracy values for M³.

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃
A ₁	-.24	-.23	.41
A ₂	-.24	.30	-.20
A ₃	.26	.09	.12
A ₄	.26	-.23	-.38

410 Step 6. Formulate the dominance matrix

411 Using Equation (3.5), we construct dominance matrix for $\alpha = 1$ The dominance matrixes are
 412 represented in matrix form (See Equations (4.4), (4.5), (4.6), (4.7), (4.8), (4.9), (4.10), (4.11), and (4.12)).

413 The dominance matrix Ψ_1^1

The dominance matrix Ψ_2^1

$$414 \quad \Psi_1^1 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & .18 & .30 & .35 \\ A_2 & -.46 & 0 & -.58 & .30 \\ A_3 & -.74 & .23 & 0 & .19 \\ A_4 & -.88 & -.74 & -.47 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

$$\Psi_2^1 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & .29 & .18 & .28 \\ A_2 & -.82 & 0 & -.69 & 0 \\ A_3 & -.51 & .24 & 0 & .29 \\ A_4 & -.81 & 0 & -.65 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.5)$$

415 The dominance matrix Ψ_3^1

The dominance matrix Ψ_1^2

$$416 \quad \Psi_3^1 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 \\ A_2 & .25 & 0 & .26 & 0 \\ A_3 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 \\ A_4 & .25 & 0 & .26 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.6)$$

$$\Psi_1^2 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & -.46 & -.88 & -.74 \\ A_2 & .18 & 0 & -.75 & -.58 \\ A_3 & .35 & .09 & 0 & .04 \\ A_4 & .30 & .23 & .19 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.7)$$

417 The dominance matrix Ψ_2^2

418
$$\Psi_2^2 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & 0 & -.84 & 0 \\ A_2 & 0 & 0 & -.84 & 0 \\ A_3 & .29 & .29 & 0 & .29 \\ A_4 & 0 & 0 & -.84 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.8)$$

The dominance matrix Ψ_3^2

419
$$\Psi_3^2 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & 0 & .26 & 0 \\ A_2 & 0 & 0 & .26 & 0 \\ A_3 & -1 & -1 & 0 & -1 \\ A_4 & 0 & 0 & .26 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.9)$$

419 The dominance matrix Ψ_1^3

420
$$\Psi_1^3 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & 0 & -.78 & -.78 \\ A_2 & 0 & 0 & -.78 & -.78 \\ A_3 & .31 & .31 & 0 & 0 \\ A_4 & .31 & .31 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.10)$$

The dominance matrix Ψ_2^3

421
$$\Psi_2^3 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & -.83 & -.65 & 0 \\ A_2 & .29 & 0 & .18 & .29 \\ A_3 & .23 & -.51 & 0 & .23 \\ A_4 & 0 & -.83 & -.65 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.11)$$

421 The dominance matrix Ψ_3^3

422
$$\Psi_3^3 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & -.94 & -.59 & -1.1 \\ A_2 & .23 & 0 & -.73 & .15 \\ A_3 & -.59 & .18 & 0 & .23 \\ A_4 & -1.1 & -.58 & -.94 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.12)$$

423 Step 7. Formulate the individual overall dominance matrix

424 The individual overall dominance matrix is calculated by the Equation (3.6) and The dominance
425 matrixes are represented in matrix form (see Equations (4.13), (4.14), and (4.15)).

426 First decision maker's overall dominance matrix λ^1

427
$$\lambda^1 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & -.53 & .47 & -.37 \\ A_2 & -1 & 0 & -1 & .30 \\ A_3 & -1.3 & -.53 & 0 & -.52 \\ A_4 & -1.5 & -.74 & -.86 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.13)$$

428 Second decision maker's overall dominance matrix λ^2

429
$$\lambda^2 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & -.46 & -1.5 & -.74 \\ A_2 & .18 & 0 & -1.3 & -.58 \\ A_3 & -.36 & -.62 & 0 & -.67 \\ A_4 & .30 & .23 & -.39 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.14)$$

430 Third decision maker's overall dominance matrix λ^3

431
$$\lambda^3 = \begin{pmatrix} & A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & -1.8 & -2 & -1.9 \\ A_2 & .52 & 0 & -1.3 & -.34 \\ A_3 & -.05 & -.02 & 0 & .46 \\ A_4 & -.79 & -.11 & -1.6 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.15)$$

432 Step 8. Aggregate the dominance matrix

433 Using Equation (3.7), the aggregate dominance matrix is constructed (see Equation 4.16).

434 Aggregate the dominance matrix λ

$$435 \quad \lambda = \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & A_2 & A_3 & A_4 \\ A_1 & 0 & -.94 & -1.1 & -.53 \\ A_2 & -.10 & 0 & -1.23 & -.22 \\ A_3 & -.54 & -.38 & 0 & -.23 \\ A_4 & -.64 & -.55 & -.96 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.16)$$

436 Step 9. Calculate global values

437 Using Equation (3.8) we calculate the values of Ω_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) and represented in Table 7.

438 Table 7. Global values of alternatives

A_i	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4
Ω_i	.49	.61	1	0

439 Step 10. Rank the priority

440 Since $\Omega_3 > \Omega_2 > \Omega_1 > \Omega_4$, alternatives are then preference ranked as follows:

441 $A_3 > A_2 > A_1 > A_4$.

442 Hence A_3 is the best alternative.

443 From the illustrative example, we see that the proposed NC-TODIM method is more suitable for real
 444 scientific and engineering applications because it can handle hybrid information consisting of INS
 445 and SVNS information simultaneously to cope indeterminate and inconsistent information. Thus,
 446 NC-TODIM extends the existing decision-making methods and provides a sophisticated
 447 mathematical tool for decision makers.

448 5. Rank of alternatives with different values of α

449 Table 8 shows that the ranking order of alternatives depends on values of attenuation factor, which reflects the
 450 importance of attenuation factor in NC-TODIM method.

451

452 Table 8. Global values and ranking of alternatives for different values of α

Values of α	Global values of alternative (Ω_i)	Rank order of A_i
0.5	$\Omega_1 = 0, \Omega_2 = .89, \Omega_3 = 1, \Omega_4 = .46$ $\Omega_3 > \Omega_2 > \Omega_4 > \Omega_1$	$A_3 > A_2 > A_4 > A_1$
1	$\Omega_1 = .49, \Omega_2 = .61, \Omega_3 = 1, \Omega_4 = 0$ $\Omega_3 > \Omega_2 > \Omega_1 > \Omega_4$	$A_3 > A_2 > A_1 > A_4$
1.5	$\Omega_1 = 0, \Omega_2 = .72, \Omega_3 = 1, \Omega_4 = .44$ $\Omega_3 > \Omega_2 > \Omega_4 > \Omega_1$	$A_3 > A_2 > A_4 > A_1$
2	$\Omega_1 = 0, \Omega_2 = 1, \Omega_3 = .81, \Omega_4 = .38$ $\Omega_2 > \Omega_3 > \Omega_4 > \Omega_1$	$A_2 > A_3 > A_4 > A_1$

3	$\Omega_1 = 0, \Omega_2 = .56, \Omega_3 = 1, \Omega_4 = .45$ $\Omega_3 > \Omega_2 > \Omega_4 > \Omega_1$	$A_3 > A_2 > A_4 > A_1$
---	---	-------------------------

453 5.1. Analysis on influence of the parameter α to ranking order

454 The impact of parameter α on ranking order is examined by comparing the ranking orders taken
 455 with varying the different values of α . When $\alpha = .5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3$, ranking order are presented in
 456 Table 8. We draw Figure 3 and Figure 4 to compare the ranking order for different values of α .
 457 When $\alpha = .5, \alpha = 1.5$ and $\alpha = 3$ the ranking order is unchanged and A_3 is the best alternative, A_1 is
 458 the worst alternative. When $\alpha = 1$, the ranking order is changed and A_3 is the best alternative and A_4
 459 is the worst alternative. For $\alpha = 2$, the ranking order is changed and A_2 is the best alternative and A_1
 460 is the worst alternative. From Table 8 we see that A_3 is the best alternative in four cases and A_1 is the
 461 worst. We can say that ranking order depends on parameter α and A_3 is the best alternative and A_1
 462 is the worst alternative.

463

464

465 **Figure.3.** Global values of the alternatives for different values of attenuation factor $\alpha = .5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3$.

466

467

468

469 **Figure.4.** Ranking of the alternatives for $\alpha = .5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3$.470 **6. Conclusion**

471 In many real world decision-making problems, decision makers encounter uncertain decision
 472 parameters that are incomplete, indeterminate and inconsistent in nature. As a result, the decision
 473 makers cannot easily reflect their judgments on the alternatives with exact and crisp values. To
 474 tackle the situation, we propose the NC-TODIM for MAGDM problems under neutrosophic cubic
 475 information, where the preference values of alternatives over the attributes and the importance of
 476 attributes are expressed in terms of neutrosophic cubic numbers. In this study, we propose score
 477 function, accuracy functions and established some of their properties. We develop NC-TODIM
 478 method, which is capable to tackle MAGDM problems affected by uncertainty and indeterminacy
 479 represented by neutrosophic cubic numbers. The standard TODIM, in its original formulation, is
 480 only applicable to a crisp environment. Existing neutrosophic TODIM methods deal with single
 481 valued neutrosophic information only. Therefore, NC-TODIM provides more flexibility to deal with
 482 real world problems. We solve a numerical example to show the applicability and effectiveness of
 483 the proposed NC-TODIM. We investigate the influence of attenuation factor of losses α on ranking
 484 order of alternatives. The proposed NC-TODIM method can be applied to other MAGDM problems
 485 characterized by neutrosophic hybrid environments.

486 **Acknowledgments:** The authors would like to acknowledge the constructive comments and suggestions of the
 487 anonymous referees.

488 **Author Contributions:** "Surapati Pramanik conceived and designed the problem; Shyamal Dalapati
 489 solved the problem; Surapati Pramanik, Shariful Alam and Tapan Kumar Roy analyzed the results;
 490 Surapati Pramanik and Shyamal Dalapati wrote the paper."

491 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest for publication of the
 492 article.

493 **References**

- 494 1. Zadeh, L.A. Fuzzy sets. *Inf. Control* 1965, 8, 338–356.
 495 2. Chen, S. J.; Hwang, C. L. *Fuzzy multiple attribute decision-making, methods and applications*. Lecture Notes in
 496 Economics and Mathematical Systems, vol. 375, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg; 1992.

- 497 3. Chang, T. H.; Wang, T. C. Using the fuzzy multi-criteria decision making approach for measuring the
498 possibility of successful knowledge management. *Inf. Sci.* 2009, 179, 355–370.
- 499 4. Krohling, R.A.; De Souza, T.T.M. Combining prospect theory and fuzzy numbers to multi-criteria
500 decision making. *Exp. Syst. Appl.* 2012, 39, 11487–11493.
- 501 5. Chen, C. T. Extension of the TOPSIS for group decision-making under fuzzy environment. *Fuzzy Sets*
502 *Syst.* 2000, 114, 1–9.
- 503 6. Zhang, G.; Lu, J. An integrated group decision-making method dealing with fuzzy preferences for
504 alternatives and individual judgments for selection criteria. *Group. Deci. Nego.* 2003, 12, 501-515.
- 505 7. Krohling, R.A.; Campanharo, V.C. Fuzzy TOPSIS for group decision making: A case study for accidents
506 with oil spill in the sea. *Exp. Syst. Appl.* 2011, 38, 4190-4197.
- 507 8. Xia, M.; Xu, Z. A novel method for fuzzy multi-criteria decision making. *Int. J. Inf. Tech. Decis.* 2014, 13, 3,
508 497–519.
- 509 9. Mehlawat, M. K.; Gupta, P. A new fuzzy group multi-criteria decision making method with an
510 application to the critical path selection. *Int J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 2015. DOI 10.1007/s00170-015-7610-4.
- 511 10. Atanassov, K. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 1986, 20, 87–96.
- 512 11. Xu, Z. Some similarity measures of intuitionistic fuzzy sets and their applications to multiple attribute
513 decision making. *Fuzzy Opt. Decis. Making.* 2007, 6, 109-121.
- 514 12. Mondal, K. Pramanik, S. Intuitionistic fuzzy multi criteria group decision making approach to
515 quality-brick selection problem. *J. Appl. Quant. Methods.* 2014, 9, 35-50.
- 516 13. Dey, P.P.; Pramanik, S.; Giri, B.C. Multi-criteria group decision making in intuitionistic fuzzy environment
517 based on grey relational analysis for weaver selection in Khadi institution. *J. Appl. Quant. Methods.* 2015, 10,
518 1-14.
- 519 14. Smarandache, F. *A unifying field in logics. In Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic probability, set and logic*; American
520 Research Press: Rehoboth, DE, USA, 1999.
- 521 15. Wang, H.; Smarandache, F.; Zhang, Y.Q.; Sunderraman, R. Single valued neutrosophic sets. *Multispace*
522 *multistructure* 2010, 4, 410–413.
- 523 16. Wang, H.; Smarandache, F.; Zhang, Y.Q.; Sunderraman, R. *Interval neutrosophic sets and logic: Theory and*
524 *applications in computing*; Hexis: Phoenix, AZ, USA, 2005.
- 525 17. Kharal, A. A neutrosophic multi-criteria decision making method. *New Math. Natural Comput.* 2014, 10,
526 143–162.
- 527 18. Ye, J. Similarity measures between interval neutrosophic sets and their multi criteria decision-making
528 method. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 2014, 26,165-172.
- 529 19. Şahin, R. Multi-criteria neutrosophic decision making method based on score and accuracy functions
530 under neutrosophic environment. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.5202>.
- 531 20. Pramanik, S.; Biswas, P.; Giri, B. C. Hybrid vector similarity measures and their applications to
532 multi-attribute decision making under neutrosophic environment. *Neural Comput. Appl.* 2015.
533 doi:10.1007/s00521-015-2125-3.
- 534 21. Ye, J. Multiple attribute group decision-making method with completely unknown weights based on
535 similarity measures under single valued neutrosophic environment. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 2014, 27,
536 2927-2935.
- 537 22. Ye, J. An extended TOPSIS method for multiple attribute group decision making based on single valued
538 neutrosophic linguistic numbers. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 2015, 28, 247–255.

- 539 23. Biswas, P.; Pramanik, S.; Giri, B. C. TOPSIS method for multi-attribute group decision-making under
540 single-valued neutrosophic environment. *Neural Comput. Appl.* 2016, 27, 727-737.
- 541 24. Ali, M.; Deli, I.; Smarandache, F. The theory of neutrosophic cubic sets and their applications in pattern
542 recognition. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 2016, 30, 1957-1963.
- 543 25. Jun, Y. B.; Smarandache, F.; Kim, C. S. Neutrosophic Cubic sets. *New Math. Natural Comput.* 2017, 13, 41-54.
- 544 26. Banerjee, D.; Giri, B. C.; , Pramanik, S.; Smarandache, F. GRA for multi attribute decision making in
545 neutrosophic cubic set environment. *Neutrosophic Sets syst.* 2017, 15, 60-69. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.570938.
- 546 27. Deng, J. L. Introduction to grey system theory. *The J. Grey Syst.* 1989, 1, 1–24.
- 547 28. Pramanik, S.; Mukhopadhyaya, D. Grey relational analysis based intuitionistic fuzzy multi criteria group
548 decision-making approach for teacher selection in higher education. *Int. J. Comp. Appl.* 2011, 34, 21–29.
- 549 29. Pramanik, S.; Dalapati, S.; Alam, S.; Roy, T. K.; Smarandache, F. neutrosophic cubic MCGDM method
550 based on similarity measure. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2017, 16, 44-56. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.831934.
- 551 30. Lu, Z.; Ye, J. Cosine measures of neutrosophic cubic sets for multiple attribute decision-making. *Symmetry*,
552 2017, 9, 121. doi:10.3390/sym9070121.
- 553 31. Pramanik, S.; Dey, P. P.; Giri, B. C.; Smarandache, F. An extended TOPSIS for multi-attribute decision
554 making problems with neutrosophic cubic information. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2017, 17, 20-28.
- 555 32. Zhan, J.; Khan, M.; Gulistan, M. Applications of neutrosophic cubic sets in multi-criteria decision-making.
556 *Int. J. Uncertain Quantif.* 2017, 7, 377-394.
- 557 33. Ye, J. Linguistic neutrosophic cubic numbers and their multiple attribute decision-making method.
558 *Information* 2017, 8, 110. doi:10.3390/info8030110.
- 559 34. Gomes, L.; Lima, M. TODIM: Basics and application to multicriteria ranking of projects with
560 environmental impacts. *Found. Comput. Decis. Sci.* 1991, 16, 113–127.
- 561 35. Kahneman, D.; Tversky, A. Prospect theory: an analysis of decision under risk. *Econom. J. Econom. Soc.*
562 1979, 47, 263–291.
- 563 36. Krohling, R.A.; De Souza, T.T.M. Combining prospect theory and fuzzy numbers to multi-criteria
564 decision making. *Exp. Syst. Appl.* 2012, 39, 11487–11493.
- 565 37. Liu, P.; Teng, F. An extended TODIM method for multiple attribute group decision-making based on
566 2-dimension uncertain linguistic Variable. *Complexity* 2014, 21, 20–30.
- 567 38. Tosun, O.; Akyu, G. A fuzzy TODIM approach for the supplier selection problem. *Int. J. Comput. Int. Syst.*
568 2015, 8, 317–329.
- 569 39. Gomes, L. F. A. M.; Machado, M. A. S.; Da Costa F. F.; Rangel, L. A. D. Criteria interactions in multiple
570 criteria decision aiding: a Choquet formulation for the TODIM method. *Procedia Computer Science* 2013,
571 17, 324–331.
- 572 40. Fan, Z.P.; Zhang, X.; Chen, F.D.; Liu, Y. Extended TODIM method for hybrid multiple attribute decision
573 making problems. *Knowl. Based. Syst.* 2013, 42, 40–48.
- 574 41. Krohling, R.A.; Pacheco, A.G.C.; Siviero, A.L.T. IF-TODIM: An intuitionistic fuzzy TODIM to
575 multi-criteria decision making. *Knowl. Based. Syst.* 2013, 53, 142–146.
- 576 42. Wang, J. Q. TODIM method with multi-valued neutrosophic set. *Cont. Decis.* 2015. DOI: 0.13195/j.kzyjc.
577 2014.0467.
- 578 43. Zhang, M.; Liu, P.; Shi, L. An extended multiple attribute group decision-making TODIM method based
579 on the neutrosophic numbers. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 2016, 30, 1773–1781. DOI: 10.3233/IFS-151889.

- 580 44. Ji, P.; Zhang, H.; Wang, J. A projection-based TODIM method under multi-valued neutrosophic
581 environments and its application in personnel selection. *Neural Comput. Appl.* 2016. DOI
582 10.1007/s00521-016-2436-z.
- 583 45. Xu, D. S.; Wei, C.; Wei, G. W. TODIM method for single-valued neutrosophic multiple attribute decision
584 making. *Information* 2017, 8, 125. doi:10.3390/info8040125.